

Human Performance Models as Semi-Autonomous Agents

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Abstract

In this paper I provide an overview of our research program by focusing on design issues associated with developing human performance models as a collection of interactive agents. I describe a cognitive architecture which formalizes the interdependencies among the semi-autonomous agents comprising the human performance model. In addition, since human performance models must be specified at multiple levels of abstraction to distinguish between the psychological model being proposed and the simulation of the model within a computer, I discuss issues associated with mapping a psychological model, stated in computational terms, into a computer simulation of the model.

Introduction

We believe that designing human performance models requires model specification at three levels of abstraction: cognitive architecture, representation and algorithm, and implementation. The cognitive architecture [16, 20] establishes the tenets defining the possible relationships between knowledge sources, or agents. It delimits a design space to be investigated by providing a framework to integrate micromodels of human performance into a comprehensive information-processing model. The cognitive architecture defines the similarities within the class of human information-processing systems. In contrast, the representation and algorithm specification [10, 21] defines a specific model of how an instance (person) of the class actually processes information. At this level individual differences in functional capabilities and topographical layout of functions (within the brain) are depicted. Both the cognitive architecture and representation and algorithm specifications are psychologically real: They are hypotheses about how individuals process information. The implementation specification, in contrast, is not psychologically real. It represents a translation of the psychological model defined in the cognitive architecture and representation and algorithm specifications into a computational model. It defines how the psychological model will be simulated within a computer.

Human performance process models

We are developing human performance models to support operability analysis studies on designs for complex real-time management information systems typically found in command and control and process control applications (e.g., air traffic control) [3, 20]. Operability analysis investigates the optimum crew composition, crew sizing, and allocation of functions between humans and machines. During operability analysis, experimental studies are conducted on alternative designs to determine crew workload, the probability of errors occurring and general ease of use. The goal is to identify and rectify design flaws early in the design process.

Traditionally, human performance models employed in engineering studies are analytic models which utilize a mathematical function to map a stimulus-input to a response-output. These mathematical functions are derived from experimental studies which present a representative set of stimuli to a representative sample of personnel while carefully measuring individual responses. The collected data is analyzed to define a mathematical function which captures this input-output relationship.

There are, however, two problems with analytic models. First, analytic models are difficult to generalize. To employ an analytic model in a design study, you must first determine if the model is valid for the tasks to be studied in the new system. Often the model is not, requiring time-consuming and expensive experimental studies to generalize the model. Second, analytic models are very poor at modeling multi-task behavior. If the new system requires the operators to concurrently perform multiple tasks there may not be any good (validated) models available.

To overcome the limitations of conventional modeling approaches to human performance we began investigating the development of human performance process (HPP) models. HPP models [3, 20] depict the *process* of information flow and transformation through the information-processing system, as well as the underlying *devices* which process and transform the information. HPP models participate in operability analysis by serving as team members in a multi-crew

environment. The HPP models interact with humans-in-the-loop through voice generation and recognition systems and through the human-system interface that they are "operating". In this capacity, the HPP models reduce experimental variability by providing behavioral replication (on the part of the team members) across simulation trials and decrease the study costs by reducing the number of personnel needed to participate in design studies.

Our first HPP model was developed by BBN Systems and Technologies [3]. This model consists of four subcomponent models: visual, auditory, cognitive, and psychomotor. The visual subcomponent models two types of visual processing: active gaze and monitoring. Active gaze represents focused and directed movement to a target point; monitoring represents a scanning process. The parameters modeled for both active gaze and monitoring are field of view, velocity of motion, saccade, and fixation pause. The auditory subcomponent models the communication protocol employed by human operators, and the bandwidth and memory limits of human auditory processing capabilities. The cognitive subcomponent model depicts cognitive activity via a procedural representation consisting of "If some condition exists Then execute some action" statements, and an inferencing engine which controls the application of the If/Then statements (normally called productions). In addition to the subcomponent models, each operator model has an individually defined, updatable world representation which is a description of the world as the operator knows it. It contains rules for decisions, an awareness of external events as seen through the operator's perceptual processes (i.e., audition and vision subcomponent models), and a declarative description of the world as the operator knows it.

The HPP model works in the following way. Information enters the world representation through the perceptual modalities. The cognitive subcomponent model continually tries to match condition clauses with the data in the world representation. If a match is triggered, the execution clause generates activities. These activities are then executed through the appropriate subcomponent model. The execution of activities can also change data in the world representation, often resulting in the generation of additional activities.

This first generation HPP model was twice tested against human operators. In both instances the performance of the HPP model was comparable to the human operators for procedural tasks. (Procedural tasks, in this instance, are tasks whose performance requirements can be defined in a decision tree of less than 500 rules). In reviewing the performance of the model, however, we realized that in order to achieve the behavioral level of sophistication required to employ the model in operability research we would need a radically different architecture for HPP model development.

We believe that to model human behavior at a level of sophistication sufficient to make design decisions several

goals have to be met. These goals fall into two categories: behavioral and structural. Behavioral goals arise from the inability of the current generation of models to predict human performance. Behavioral goals include building models that can characterize performance limitations due to high task demands, skill-level differences between personnel, concurrent task performance, and complex decision-making.

Structural goals stem from a lack of sophistication in depicting the information-processing system. Lack of structural sophistication is the primary constraint preventing the development of models embodying complex behaviors. Structural goals include modeling simultaneously both top-down and bottom-up information-processing, both the serial information-processing system operating within human awareness and the parallel information-processing system operating outside of human awareness, knowledge at multiple levels of abstraction, and knowledge represented in multiple formats.

To achieve these goals we are developing new cognitive and implementation architectures. The cognitive architecture is based upon Koestler's theory of the mind [8, 9]. Koestler proposes that the mind consists of semi-autonomous centers (called holons) arranged into hierarchy (called a holarchy). The implementation architecture is based upon Hewitt's Actor programming model [7]. Actors are interactive, encapsulated, modules which communicate through asynchronous message passing.

The holon cognitive architecture

Individual holons (centers, or agents) behave as if they were quasi-autonomous wholes. For example, each holon displays its own timing basis for patterns of activity. In addition, each holon has its own internal representation (working memory) of the environment. The "environment" for a holon may be the external world, the internal system, or both. Holons represent only that portion of the environment that is relevant to them in performing their function. Further, different holons can represent information at different levels of abstraction, and in different formats.

A holon's behavior is governed by fixed rules (collectively called the holon's canon), which are executed through flexible strategies. The execution of the canon is dependent upon the holon's environment. Hence, holons can potentially generate a wide range of behaviors from a limited instruction set (canon) due to the diversity of the environment. Different environmental conditions invoke different holon activity. This gives holons great behavioral flexibility.

Holons communicate through message passing. They employ three types of message passing: hierarchical, broadcast, and point-to-point. Hierarchical message paths define parent/child relationships. Broadcast messages go from one holon to all others. Point-to-point

messages go from one holon to another holon or to a specific set of holons.

Holons are arranged in hierarchy, called a holarchy [8, 9]. The number of levels in a holarchy is called the holarchy's depth; the number of holons on a given level is called the holarchy's span. Figure 1 is an input holarchy with a depth of three and a span of four (at its lowest level). Levels within a holarchy demarcate processing points where the level of abstraction of information changes. Typically, information comes in at one level of abstraction and through processing within the holon a new information product, usually at a different level of abstraction, is generated. Specific branches are established in a holarchy to either analyze or define specific dimensions of the signal.

Figure 1. A Visual Input holarchy

Branching lines in a holarchy represent communication channels. Holons on different levels, but within the same branch structure, normally communicate through hierarchical messages (i.e., within a branch, a holon has a special relationship with its parent and children). Holons also can communicate directly with other holons through point-to-point messages. In addition, holons can effect changes in the general environment through broadcast messages to all other holons.

There are different classes of holarchies. The two most common classes are input holarchies and output holarchies. Input holarchies convert complex input patterns into symbolic representations. Each level of an input holarchy acts as a filter or classifier, identifying the input signal as some higher order construct. The abstracted knowledge of that construct is then passed up the holarchy.

Output holarchies work inversely; whereas an input holarchy abstracts information, an output holarchy elaborates, or embellishes, information. A simple signal called the trigger releaser can cause the output holarchy to perform complex actions. The releaser concept is analogous to the forming of an intention. Once the "intention" activates the holarchy, holons on each successively lower level of the output holarchy further define and specify the action being undertaken.

The holon theory provides a framework within which to develop sophisticated HPP models. The holon cognitive architecture supports models employing multiple data streams and processing centers, thus allowing a developer to create models which incorporate top-down and bottom-up processing, and serial and parallel information-processing sub-component models. Further, because holons are encapsulated, semi-autonomous wholes, individual holons can represent and employ knowledge in different formats (e.g., semantic nets, productions, etc.). Finally, the holarchy structure provides a means of creating models which represent knowledge at different levels of abstraction.

Operator model architecture

Supporting the cognitive architecture is the implementation architecture [5, 20]. The implementation architecture provides the tools to realize instantiations of the cognitive architecture in a simulation. An implementation architecture [19] typically consists of a programming language and additional tools to support building, running, and analyzing HPP models. We are in the process of developing an implementation architecture called the Operator Model Architecture (OMAR) through a contract to BBN Systems and Technologies [5].

The basic building blocks of OMAR are a frame language with graphical editing environment, a procedure language with a browser and graphical editor, an interactive real-time execution environment to drive the simulation and provide insights into the activities and agents, and an interactive post-run analysis capability to support analysis of agent/holon actions in more detail.

The frame language provides the ability to define agents and objects in the domain being investigated. In addition, it provides an efficient link to the message passing and other generic functions in the underlying programming language (which is the Common Lisp Object System [CLOS]). Finally, the frame language provides the ability to perform semantic net activation and inferencing.

The procedural language provides procedure definitions for networks which instantiate holon functionality. The language is readily extensible, supporting the addition of new functionality. One extension under development is a rule-based language to support research on decision-making behavior. In addition, the development of a graphical editor is planned to support model set-up and maintenance.

The interactive runtime environment provides control of HPP model execution, a variable filter recorder to capture the audit trail of a simulation run, a variable filter trace to provide on-line insight into agent/holon performance (as well as debugging support), and a timeline display with the ability to interactively pursue agent behavior forward and backward in time.

The runtime environment, in addition, features an interface to a system modeling testbed, called the

Operability Assessment System (OASYS). OASYS is a tool box that designers employ to investigate operability issues on management information systems by creating a "soft" prototype of the design under consideration. The OASYS tool box contains requirements definition tools, rapid prototyping tools, system emulation libraries, human-in-loop simulation tools, and data collection and analysis tools. All modules are integrated through a modular software framework that allows an analyst to "plug in" needed modules. When OASYS is emulating a multi-crew environment, OASYS either can provide crew stations for each human-in-the-loop operator, or allow OMAR to be linked to the simulation, letting HPP models operate some of the consoles. To support linkage to OASYS, the OMAR run-time environment provides capabilities to partially "bootstrap" the HPP models with appropriate knowledge, an ability to time-synchronize the two simulation environments, and the interface methods to allow OMAR-built HPP models to receive and respond to OASYS console state changes (i.e., changes in the information being displayed).

Developing human performance models

We call our approach to developing HPP models the method of successive approximation [21]. This method adapts the incremental model of systems development to the development of HPP models. Incremental system development requires a series of development cycles where, during each iteration, a complete system (e.g., HPP model) is built. In a traditional incremental system development each subsequent development cycle enhances the functionality of the system; in an incremental HPP model development each subsequent development cycle extends the resolution of the model.

During each development cycle a complete HPP model is developed. Initial models may, however, have some sub-component models where the information-processing stages are depicted at a low level of resolution; that is, instead of depicting all the stages and aspects of information transformation for a given subsystem (e.g., vision), an initial model might aggregate several stages into one combined stage. Subsequent iterations of development extend the resolution of the model by expanding aggregated stages into fully developed process models.

There are two other significant differences in the design phase between the method of successive approximation and traditional iterative system development. First, in developing an HPP model the designer does not start with a "clean sheet of paper". Rather, the designer starts with a cognitive architecture. The cognitive architecture is a design space, or framework, into which existing psychological micromodels are mapped. Typically, these micromodels depict a limited aspect, or a specific stage, of the information-processing system. In designing an HPP model the model developer must integrate these

micromodels into the cognitive architecture. In this capacity the cognitive architecture provides a set of constraints--defined by the architectural tenets (e.g., the requirement that different branches of the hierarchy analyze separate modalities, that each holon maintain a working memory, etc.)--on potential computational mechanisms that can underlie psychological functionality.

Second, HPP models must be specified as both a psychologically real representation of the mechanisms underlying human information-processing and a computer implementable simulation. This requires an additional phase of design work. The psychological model must first be developed, then it must be translated into a specification that can be implemented as a computer simulation.

An iterative approach to HPP model development allows us to incrementally develop, test and validate models. During each cycle, an HPP model accounting for one behavior important to the analysis of operability issues is developed and validated. An initial cycle might, for example, focus on modeling skill-level differences between novices and experts, while a later cycle might focus on modeling complex decision making. Each successive cycle extends, or refines, the initial HPP model.

Current focus of research

Our current research focus is the development of mechanisms to further constrain the cognitive architecture. The holon cognitive architecture functions as a grammar of the mind, providing a set of rules which define possible configurations of the human information-processing system. In this analogy, the tenets of the cognitive architecture correspond to the rules of the grammar. A problem identified by linguistic researchers [15] investigating universal grammar [1, 2] is that, for a grammar to be useful as a theoretical tool, it must be appropriately constrained. One justifiable criticism of the holon architecture is that, as an explanatory tool, it is too powerful in its current formulation.

The current formulation of the holon architecture is based upon Koestler's proposal for a general systems theory. The application of this theory to the development of psychological models requires additional architectural tenets, or constraints. The two most important tenets needing development are models of memory and attention.

Our research program is investigating HPP models which depict the brain as consisting of functionally separate centers which coordinate their activity through feed forward and feedback signaling. Neurologically, these centers may correspond to neuron ensembles located in the brain [4], with the coordination activity corresponding to brain waves [6]. To support research on neurologically plausible models, we are developing a

distributed model of memory and a functional model of attention.

Memory traces (or engrams) in the holon cognitive architecture are called *threads*. Threads are states that a holon can assume, where each state is the "recognition" of a pattern of environmental stimuli (e.g., an object, situation, or concept). Threads consist of thread segments, which are pointers to additional threads in other holons. Individual threads are combined into thread systems, one per holon, which define the set of objects a holon can recognize, and/or, the procedures it can execute.

To illustrate the notion of threads, consider the concept of a chair (figure 2). The chair thread is part of an object-recognition holon (which defines the objects the model can recognize). The chair thread consists of three segments: a shape, a color, and a use-of segment. The chair thread becomes active when messages received from form-recognition and color-recognition holons (figure 3) are matched by the object-recognition holon to the form and color segments of the chair thread. (Once the chair thread is active, the use-of slot might consist of a procedure which would send a message to another holon.)

Figure 2. An Object-recognition Holon

The messages received from the form-recognition and color-recognition holons do not contain color or form data, instead, they contain pointers to threads in the sending holons. The message from the form-recognition holon contains a pointer to the chair-form thread, and the message from the color-recognition holon contains a pointer to a color thread (e.g., gray). Threads within the form- and color-recognition holons also consist of thread segments, which are pointers to threads in other holons (not shown); these threads, in turn, consist of segments which are pointers to other pointers, lower in the holarchy. Thread decomposition continues until the lowest levels of the holarchy are reached.

The data which comprise an active thread are distributed among the constellation of active holons. The state of any active holon is defined by the patterns it is recognizing at the moment; holons change states as different patterns are recognized. Analogously, holon state changes represent changes in the activation levels of neuron ensembles in the brain. The thread model of memory is at once dynamic and neurologically plausible.

Figure 3. Three Holons

The intellectual antecedents of threads include frame and knowledge-line concepts from artificial intelligence [12], and models of category structure [e.g., 11] from cognitive psychology. Threads, like frames, define ecologically important patterns by providing the structures necessary to describe the patterns. In addition, thread segments, like frame-slots, have entry conditions and default values associated with them; though, in a thread model of memory, the default value of a segment is a pointer to a thread in another holon, not to a stored value. Further, thread systems differ from frame systems in that threads are inherently distributed structures (distributed across the holons comprising the holarchy) and that they represent knowledge at multiple levels of abstraction. Finally, thread systems differ from frame systems in that they are explicitly designed to investigate models of category structure in a distributed network [14].

The data in individual holons define what the model "knows" about a specific class of information. The thread system in a form-recognition holon, for example,

contains the set of forms the model knows; it defines the set of forms the model can recognize. Within each holon, class instances are arranged in a network where distance between instances is a function of similarity, across pertinent dimensions. The thread model of memory allows depiction of basic, supraordinate, and subordinate categorical relationships [17] within a holon, and other associative relationships--among distinct classes of information--across the holarchy.

Holon-based HPP models require a functional model of attention [13]. To achieve this, we are developing a model of attention which operates by spreading excitation and inhibition between holons. The process begins with the matching of incoming stimuli--coming from manifold holons--to the holon's threads. Next, as threads become active, the holon sends excitatory feedback to those holons providing input for the active threads and inhibitory feedback to the other signaling holons. In addition, thread activation triggers a procedure which feeds forward recognition of the event or pattern upwards in the holarchy. As holons higher in the holarchy, in turn, identify patterns they feed back excitatory or inhibitory signals to the active holons. Eventually, the upwards moving signal reaches a holon whose activation triggers a behavior (e.g., some form of motor activity).

The above description is a simplified description of the attentional process being developed for the holon cognitive architecture. Our goal is to develop an attentional process that can produce coherent, emergent, behavior from the activity of independent, asynchronous, modules without requiring a centralized control mechanism, like those used in blackboard or production system research.

To firmly anchor the thread model of memory and the functional model of attention in psychological data, we are developing a holon-based model of visual processing combining feature-integration theory [18] and the process of perceptual microgenesis [9]. We are using the experimental results underpinning these theories to constrain our models of memory and attention. Once an HPP model is developed that satisfies the requirements of visual processing (as defined in these theories) we will then generalize the models of memory and attention to other, more cognitively-based, information-processing activities and behaviors.

The models of memory and attention described above are psychological models. Once the psychological models are developed, computational methods must be developed to implement the mechanisms in a runnable simulation. These computational (or, implementational) methods will provide the means to selectively attenuate or enhance information (messages) coming from specific holons. The basis of these mechanisms will probably be distinct message types along with special message-handling logic incorporated into each holon's message port.

The addition of psychologically and neurologically plausible models of memory and attention to the holon cognitive architecture and its implementation in the Operator Model Architecture will create a powerful instrument for cognitive science research. The holon cognitive architecture supports psychological research on distributed associative models of memory, functional models of attention, and hierarchical models of information-processing; all at a symbolic level of representation. The Operator Model Architecture supports artificial intelligence research on Actor-based simulations and distributed control mechanisms. Together, they support the development of a new generation of human performance models as semi-autonomous agents.

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